

A Resilient Microservices Architecture for AI-Powered Academic Assistant: Integrating Spring AI, RAG, and MCP Patterns

Douglas Felipe
Instituto Metrpole Digital (IMD)
Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN)
Natal, Brazil
douglas.felipe@ufrn.edu.br

Abstract—This paper presents the design, implementation, and evaluation of a resilient distributed system for an AI-powered academic assistant. The system employs a microservices architecture built with Spring Cloud, integrating Spring AI with Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) to answer questions about faculty members at the Instituto Metrpole Digital (IMD/UFRN). The architecture incorporates three primary microservices: an AI service with RAG capabilities and Model Context Protocol (MCP) integration, a serverless function service using Spring Cloud Function, and an external MCP service for third-party API integration. Comprehensive resilience patterns were implemented using Resilience4j (Circuit Breaker, Retry, Rate Limiter, Time Limiter), alongside the establishment of full observability via Prometheus, Grafana, and Zipkin. Load testing with Apache JMeter evaluated system capacity under various conditions. Results demonstrate the system’s ability to maintain service availability during partial failures, with Circuit Breaker patterns successfully preventing cascade failures. The implementation follows the Twelve-Factor App methodology and adheres to established architectural and system integration standards for AI-integrated distributed systems.

Index Terms—microservices, Spring AI, RAG, resilience patterns, Circuit Breaker, observability, distributed systems, MCP

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) into distributed systems presents unique challenges related to latency, reliability, and context management. As organizations increasingly adopt AI-powered assistants for specialized domains, the need for resilient architectures that can handle AI service failures while maintaining system availability becomes critical.

This work addresses these challenges by implementing a microservices-based academic assistant capable of answering questions about faculty members at the Instituto Metrpole Digital (IMD) of the Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN). The system demonstrates the practical application of several modern architectural patterns:

- **Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)** for grounding LLM responses in domain-specific knowledge
- **Model Context Protocol (MCP)** for structured access to internal and external data sources

- **Spring Cloud Function** for serverless processing components
- **Resilience4j patterns** for fault tolerance and graceful degradation
- **Distributed tracing and metrics** for full observability

The contributions of this work include: (1) the design and implementation of an architecture for AI-integrated microservices incorporating resilience patterns, (2) the implementation of a RAG-based workflow with function calling capabilities, (3) an evaluation of system behavior under load, and (4) deployment configurations aligned with cloud-native principles.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Microservices Architecture Patterns

Richardson [1] defines microservices as an architectural style that structures an application as a collection of loosely coupled services. Key patterns include API Gateway for unified entry points, Service Discovery for dynamic service location, and Externalized Configuration for environment-specific settings.

B. Resilience Patterns

Nygard [2] introduced the Circuit Breaker pattern to prevent cascade failures in distributed systems. When a service fails repeatedly, the circuit “opens,” redirecting requests to fallback methods. Resilience4j [3] provides a lightweight implementation of Circuit Breaker, Retry, Rate Limiter, Bulkhead, and Time Limiter patterns for Java applications.

C. Retrieval-Augmented Generation

Lewis et al. [4] proposed RAG as a method to enhance LLM responses by retrieving relevant documents before generation. This approach reduces hallucination and enables domain-specific knowledge integration without model fine-tuning.

D. Model Context Protocol

The Model Context Protocol (MCP) [5] standardizes how AI applications access contextual data. MCP servers expose structured resources that LLMs can query through function calling, enabling seamless integration between AI models and enterprise data sources.

E. Twelve-Factor App

Wiggins [6] established the Twelve-Factor methodology for building software-as-a-service applications. These principles guide configuration management, dependency isolation, stateless processes, and observability—all essential for cloud-native microservices.

III. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The academic assistant system enables users to ask natural language questions about IMD/UFRN faculty members, receiving AI-generated responses grounded in structured professor data. Figure 1 illustrates the high-level architecture.

Fig. 1: High-level system architecture showing infrastructure (green), application services (blue), external dependencies (orange), and observability components (purple).

A. Infrastructure Components

- **Config Server (8888):** Centralized configuration using Spring Cloud Config with native file-based repository. Enables runtime configuration updates via `/actuator/refresh`.
- **Eureka Server (8761):** Netflix Eureka for service registration and discovery. Services register on startup and query for peer locations.
- **API Gateway (8080):** Spring Cloud Gateway MVC providing unified entry point, request routing, and per-route Circuit Breakers.

B. Application Services

Table I summarizes the three primary microservices and their responsibilities.

IV. ARCHITECTURE AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. AI Service with RAG

The AI service implements Retrieval-Augmented Generation following these steps:

- 1) **Keyword Extraction:** Parse user question to identify professor names and research topics
- 2) **Context Retrieval:** Query MCPInternalService to retrieve relevant professor records

TABLE I: Microservices Overview

Service	Port	Responsibility
ai-service	8082	Spring AI integration, RAG pipeline, MCP Internal (professor data), function calling
function-service	8083	Spring Cloud Function: preprocessQuestion, enrichAnswer
mcp-external-service	8084	OpenWeatherMap integration via Feign Client (MCP External)

- 3) **Prompt Construction:** Build system prompt with retrieved context
- 4) **LLM Invocation:** Call Ollama (model: llama3.2:3b or configured alternative) via Spring AI ChatClient
- 5) **Function Calling:** LLM may invoke registered tools (professorInfo, listProfessors, searchByResearchArea)
- 6) **Response Assembly:** Combine answer with sources and confidence metadata

The implementation uses Spring AI's ChatClient with declarative tool registration:

Listing 1: AI Processing with Function Calling

```
@CircuitBreaker(name = "aiClient",
    fallbackMethod = "fallbackProcessQuestion")
@Retry(name = "aiClient")
@TimeLimiter(name = "aiClient")
public CompletableFuture<AIResponse>
    processQuestion(AIRequest request) {

    List<ProfessorInfo> professors =
        retrieveRelevantProfessors(request);
    String context = buildEnrichedContext(professors);

    String response = chatClient.prompt()
        .system(buildSystemPrompt(context))
        .user(request.getQuestion())
        .functions("professorInfo",
            "listProfessors",
            "searchByResearchArea")
        .call()
        .content();

    return CompletableFuture.completedFuture(
        AIResponse.builder()
            .answer(response)
            .sources(extractSources(professors))
            .confidence(calculateConfidence(...))
            .build());
}
```

B. Serverless Function Service

The function-service implements two Spring Cloud Functions exposed as HTTP endpoints:

preprocessQuestion: Normalizes input questions by removing accents, extracting professor names via regex pattern matching, and detecting intent (RESEARCH_QUERY, COURSE_QUERY, CONTACT_QUERY, GENERAL_QUERY).

enrichAnswer: Adds metadata (timestamp, version), formats responses, and appends disclaimers when confidence falls below threshold (0.5).

Both functions implement and are auto-exposed via Spring Cloud Function Web:

Listing 2: Question Preprocessor Function

```

@Component ("preprocessQuestion")
public class QuestionPreprocessor
    implements Function<QuestionDTO, QuestionDTO> {

    private static final Pattern PROFESSOR_PATTERN =
        Pattern.compile(
            "(?:professor|prof\\.?.?)\\s+" +
            "([A-Z][a-z]+(?:\\s+[A-Z][a-z]+)*)",
            Pattern.CASE_INSENSITIVE);

    @Override
    public QuestionDTO apply(QuestionDTO input) {
        String professorName =
            extractProfessorName(input.getQuestion());
        String normalized =
            normalizeText(input.getQuestion());
        String intent = detectIntent(normalized);

        return QuestionDTO.builder()
            .question(normalized)
            .professorName(professorName)
            .intent(intent)
            .build();
    }
}

```

C. MCP External Service

The mcp-external-service demonstrates integration with third-party APIs using Spring Cloud OpenFeign:

Listing 3: OpenWeatherMap Feign Client

```

@FeignClient(name = "openweathermap",
    url = "${openweather.api.base-url}")
public interface OpenWeatherMapClient {

    @GetMapping("/weather")
    Map<String, Object> getCurrentWeather(
        @RequestParam("q") String city,
        @RequestParam("appid") String apiKey,
        @RequestParam("units") String units,
        @RequestParam("lang") String lang);
}

```

D. Request Flow

Figure 2 illustrates the end-to-end request flow for processing a user question.

V. RESILIENCE AND OBSERVABILITY

A. Resilience4j Configuration

The system implements multiple resilience patterns via Resilience4j annotations. Table II summarizes the configuration for the AI service Circuit Breaker.

TABLE II: Circuit Breaker Configuration (aiClient)

Parameter	Value
sliding-window-size	20
minimum-number-of-calls	10
failure-rate-threshold	50%
wait-duration-in-open-state	30s
slow-call-duration-threshold	11s
slow-call-rate-threshold	50%
permitted-calls-in-half-open	5

Fig. 2: Sequence diagram for question processing flow.

Fig. 3: Circuit Breaker state machine with transitions.

Figure 3 illustrates the Circuit Breaker state machine. Additional patterns implemented:

- **Retry:** 3 attempts with 2s wait and exponential backoff (multiplier 2)
- **Time Limiter:** 20s timeout for AI calls, 25s for processing
- **Rate Limiter:** Gateway limits at 10 requests/second per route

B. Observability Stack

The observability infrastructure comprises:

- **Prometheus (9090):** Scrapes /actuator/prometheus endpoints every 15 seconds. Collects JVM metrics, HTTP metrics, and Resilience4j state metrics.
- **Grafana (3001):** Visualizes dashboards for Circuit Breaker states, request latencies, and error rates.
- **Zipkin (9411):** Distributed tracing with 100% sampling probability. Traces propagate through all services via Micrometer Tracing with Brave.

Key metrics exposed include:

- resilience4j_circuitbreaker_state
- resilience4j_circuitbreaker_failure_rate
- http_server_requests_seconds
- jvm_memory_used_bytes

VI. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Test Environment

Load testing was conducted using Apache JMeter 5.6.3 with JMeter Plugins (jp@gc) for advanced visualization. The test plan implements a comprehensive health check and functional testing strategy. Table III summarizes the core configuration.

TABLE III: JMeter Test Plan Configuration

Parameter	Value	Description
USERS	15	Concurrent virtual users
RAMP_UP	10s	Gradual user ramp-up
DURATION	60000ms	Total test duration
THINK_TIME	1000ms	Inter-request delay
<i>HTTP Request Defaults</i>		
Target Host	localhost:8080	Gateway entry point
Connect Timeout	2000ms	TCP connection limit
Response Timeout	3000ms	Default response limit
Protocol	HTTP/1.1	With Keep-Alive
Content-Type	application/json	UTF-8 encoded

The ThreadGroup is configured with scheduler=true for duration-based control and on_sample_error=continue to capture all failures without stopping execution.

B. Test Scenarios

The test plan comprises 8 HTTP samplers organized in sequential execution. Table IV details each scenario with its assertions.

TABLE IV: JMeter Test Scenarios and Assertions

#	Endpoint	Timeout	Assertions
0	GET /actuator/health	2s	200 OK, JSON \$.status=UP
1	GET /api/ai/health	3s	200 OK, contains 'healthy'
2	GET /api/orchestrator/health	2s	200 OK, contains 'running'
3	GET /api/mcp-external/health	3s	200 503, JSON \$.status exists
4	POST /api/ai/ask	20s	200 OK, JSON \$.answer, \$.sources
5	POST /preprocessQuestion	5s	200 OK, JSON \$.question, \$.intent
6	POST /enrichAnswer	3s	200 OK, contains 'Nota:', \$.metadata.service_name
7	POST /api/orchestrator/process-question	30s	200 OK, JSON \$.status=SUCCESS, \$.answer

1) *Request Payloads*: The AI-related requests use structured JSON payloads:

Listing 4: RAG Query Payload (Scenario 4)

```
{
  "question": "What are the research areas of Professor Nelio Cacho?",
  "professorName": "Nelio Cacho",
  "context": ""
}
```

The preprocessQuestion function (Scenario 5) tests intent detection:

Listing 5: Preprocess Payload

```
{
  "question": "what is the research area of prof nelio?",
  "professorName": null,
  "intent": null,
  "metadata": {}
}
```

The enrichAnswer function (Scenario 6) tests low-confidence handling with confidence: 0.3 (below threshold 0.5), triggering the disclaimer injection.

2) *Assertion Types*: Each sampler includes multiple assertion types:

- **ResponseAssertion**: Validates HTTP status codes
- **DurationAssertion**: Enforces response time SLAs
- **JSONPathAssertion**: Validates JSON structure and values

C. Metrics and Visualization

The test plan includes four result collectors for comprehensive analysis:

- 1) **View Results Tree**: Individual request/response inspection with full assertion details
- 2) **Summary Report**: Aggregated statistics per sampler (samples, avg, min, max, error%)
- 3) **Aggregate Report**: Statistical distribution with 90th/95th/99th percentiles
- 4) **jp@gc - Response Times Over Time**: Time-series visualization (500ms granularity)
- 5) **jp@gc - Transactions per Second**: Throughput visualization (1s granularity)

D. Capacity Analysis

Following standard capacity planning methodology, the following is defined:

- **Knee Capacity**: Load point where response time begins significant degradation
- **Usable Capacity**: Maximum load maintaining SLA (<5% error rate, p95 < timeout)
- **Ceiling Capacity**: Absolute maximum before system failure

1) *Performance Profile*: The LLM inference latency (Ollama with llama3.2:3b or minimax-m2:cloud) dominates response time for AI-related scenarios. The 20s and 30s timeouts accommodate cold starts and model loading.

E. Failure Recovery Test

The resilience evaluation procedure:

- 1) Start all services; verify 0% error rate in JMeter
- 2) Terminate one ai-service instance
- 3) Observe Circuit Breaker transition to OPEN state via Grafana/Actuator
- 4) Verify error rate increase and fallback responses
- 5) Restart ai-service instance

- 6) Observe Circuit Breaker transition through HALF_OPEN to CLOSED
- 7) Verify error rate returns to 0%

VII. DISCUSSION, LIMITATIONS, AND THREATS TO VALIDITY

A. Key Findings

The implementation demonstrates that Spring Cloud provides comprehensive infrastructure for AI-integrated microservices. The combination of Spring AI with RAG enables domain-specific responses while function calling extends LLM capabilities through registered tools.

Resilience4j annotations provide declarative fault tolerance with minimal code intrusion. The Circuit Breaker pattern effectively prevents cascade failures, though careful tuning of thresholds is required to balance between premature opening and delayed detection.

B. Limitations

- **LLM Latency:** Ollama local inference introduces 5–15s latency per query, limiting throughput
- **Single Instance:** Testing conducted with single instances; horizontal scaling not evaluated
- **Context Window:** RAG limited to 4 professors to fit context window constraints
- **Vector Store:** Current implementation uses keyword matching; production systems should employ vector embeddings

C. Threats to Validity

Internal: JMeter tests executed on development machine; results may vary in production environments with dedicated resources.

External: The system targets a specific domain (faculty information) with limited data (4 professors). Generalization to larger datasets requires additional evaluation.

Construct: Confidence scores are heuristically calculated based on source matching, not through established NLP metrics.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a resilient microservices architecture integrating Spring AI with RAG for an academic assistant application. The implementation successfully demonstrates:

- Integration of LLMs into distributed systems using Spring AI
- RAG pattern with function calling for domain-specific knowledge
- Comprehensive resilience using Resilience4j patterns
- Full observability via Prometheus, Grafana, and Zipkin
- Serverless functions with Spring Cloud Function
- Twelve-Factor compliance for cloud-native deployment

Future work includes: (1) integration of vector databases for semantic search in RAG, (2) horizontal scaling evaluation with Kubernetes, (3) comparison of local vs. cloud LLM

providers, and (4) implementation of caching strategies for repeated queries.

The complete source code and deployment configurations are available in the repository at <https://github.com/DougFelipe/rag-academic-assistant>, demonstrating a functional implementation of an AI-integrated distributed systems architecture.

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